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C O N T E N T S

Visualization in Basic Science and Engineering Education
Rushan Ziatdinov (Ed.)

Advantages of Using the CAS Mathematica in a Study of Supplementary Chapters of Probability Theory N.M. Mezhennaya, O.V. Pugachev	4
An Essential Change to the Training of Computer Science Teachers: The Need to Learn Graphics V. Grinshkun, E. Bidaibekov, S. Koneva, G. Baidrakhmanova	25
The Applicability of Visualization Tools in the Meta-Design of an Educational Environment A.A. Zakharova, E.V. Vekhter, A.V. Shklyar	43
Visualisation as a Method for the Development of the Term Rectangle for Pupils in Primary School J. Gunčaga, K. Žilková	52
Visualisation of Selected Mathematics Concepts with Computers – the Case of Torricelli’s Method and Statistics J. Gunčaga, W. Zawadowski, T. Prodromou	69
Visualisation in Basic Science and Engineering Education of Future Primary School Teachers in Human Biology Education Using Augmented Reality M. Fuchsova, L. Korenova	92
Visual Literacy and Visualization in Instructional Design and Technology for Learning Environments Z. Güney	103

The Problems of Contemporary Education

Development of Effective Education and Training System in the Context of the Transition to International Accreditation M.N. Dudin, Y.S. Shishalova	118
Anxiety towards Mathematics: A Case of Study in High-School Students M.E. Escalera-Chávez, C.A. Rojas-Kramer	128
Effects of Education Programs on Dance Sport Performance in Youth Dancers A. Barbora P. Uspuriene, R.K. Malinauskas, S.A. Sniras	136
Modernization of Regional Continuing Pedagogical Education in the «School-College-Institute» R.S. Nagovitsyn, D.K. Bartosh, A.Y. Ratsimor, N.V. Neverova	144
Opinions of Teachers from the Central Slovak Region on Teaching Sports Games at Elementary Schools M. Nemeč, S. Adamčak, J. Michal, P. Bartik	157

The Model of the Emotionally-Valuable Component of the Content of Primary School Foreign-Language Education: Designing and Testing M.N. Tatarinova, M.G. Shvetsova	167
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The History of Education

Pedagogical Model of Integrative-Modular Training in Professional Preparation of Students I.V. Abramova, Z.V. Shilova, V.I. Varankina, I.V. Rubanova	187
Free Education: Fundamentals of Humanistic Pedagogics (on the example of Activity of the German Public Figures of the second half of XIX – the beginning of the XX centuries of F. Gansberg, L. Gurlitt, G. Sharrelman) S.I. Belentsov, A.V. Fahrutdinova, G.Y. Grevtseva, E.A. Batrachenko	201
Development of School Education in the Vologda Governorate (1725–1917). Part 1 A.A. Cherkasov, S.N. Bratanovskii, L.A. Koroleva, L.G. Zimovets	208
Apprenticeship in Secondary Vocational Schools during the Economic Modernization in late Imperial Russia. Part 2 T.A. Magsumov	215
Teacher Training for the System of Primary Education in Switzerland in the mid-nineteenth century A.M. Mamadaliev, I. Gordeev, N.V. Miku, A. Médico	222
Education Reforms in the Don Region in 1880–1890 and Host Ataman Prince N.I. Svyatopolk-Mirsky A.Yu. Peretyatko, T.E. Zulfugarzade	229
The Potential of Museums in the Mediation of Science and Technology. Museum Presentation and Education on the Example of the Technical Museum in Brno (Czech Republic) L. Jagošová, O. Kirsch, P. Tišliar	240

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Education Reforms in the Don Region in 1880–1890 and Host Ataman Prince N.I. Svyatopolk-Mirsky

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Abstract

Ataman Nikolai Ivanovich Svyatopolk-Mirsky came under harsh criticism, targeted by his contemporaries from the liberal camp, as a persecutor of enlightenment who “has failed to completely abolish science, but not thanks to the lack of enthusiasm.” On the other hand, today’s historians urge the academic community to re-assess the figure of the ataman who contributed to opening several new educational institutions on the Don. In our paper, we tried to throw light on the situation by deliberately focusing on the policy of N.I. Svyatopolk-Mirsky in education. As a result, we found out that numerous close-downs of gymnasiums, initiated by the ataman, and reduced number of students can be explained not so much by political considerations but by criminal and educational reasons, and the process began after 1885, when a gymnasium principal fled Novocherkassk following an attack by his students. At the same time, instead of closed gymnasiums, N.I. Svyatopolk-Mirsky established technical and vocational schools that were long urgently needed. Our primary conclusion is that although N.I. Svyatopolk-Mirsky pursued a logical and reasonable educational policy in general, he made a number of mistakes – he excessively cut enrolment in gymnasiums and failed to provide the region with graduates from the network of vocational schools he created.

Keywords: education on the Don in 1880-1890, Don Cossacks, N.I. Svyatopolk-Mirsky, Novocherkassk gymnasium, ataman technical school, army trades schools.

1. Introduction

The history of education in pre-revolutionary Russia is currently attracting many researchers and provoking heated debates in academia. It is clear that the image of an illiterate and ignorant country, fostered in the Soviet era, does not reflect reality. For example, A.A. Cherkasov

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GARO – Gosudarstvennyi arkhiv Rostovskoi oblasti [State archive of the Rostov region]. [in Russian]

Karasev, 1899 – *Karasev, A.A.* (1899). Donskie atamany za poslednie polveka [Don atamans over the past half century]. *Russkii arkhiv*, Kn. 2. pp. 106-116. [in Russian]

Karpenko, 2006 – *Karpenko, A.N.* (2006). Razvitie sistemy obrazovaniya v Oblasti voiska Donskogo vo 2-i polovine XIX veka [The development of the education system in the area of the Don Cossack troops in the 2nd half of the XIX century]. Donskoi yuridicheskii institut: Uchenye zapiski. Pamyati S.V. Rimskogo. T. 31. Rostov-na-Donu, pp. 229-256. [in Russian]

Khramtsov, 2018 – *Khramtsov, A.B.* (2018). Development of National Education in the Cities of Western Siberia: From Initial to General Education (1880–1917). *Bylye Gody*. 47(1): 349-359.

Krasnov, 1863 – *Krasnov, N.I.* (1863). Materialy dlya geografii i statistiki Rossii, sobrannye ofitserami General'nogo shtaba [Materials for geography and statistics of Russia, collected by officers of the General Staff]. Zemlya voiska Donskogo. SPb., 596 p. [in Russian]

Kratkie svedeniya..., 1895 – *Kratkie svedeniya o sostoyashchem, pod vysokim pokrovitel'stvom atamana vsekh kazach'ikh voisk ego imperatorskogo vysochestva naslednika tsesarevicha, Novocherkasskom Atamanskom tekhnicheskome uchilishche za vremya ego sushchestvovaniya s 1888 po 1895 g.* [Brief information about the whole Cossack troops of his imperial highness, heir to the crown Prince, Novocherkassk Ataman Technical School, under the high patronage of the Ataman Technical School during its existence from 1888 to 1895]. Novocherkassk, 1895. 62 p. [in Russian]

Maslakovets, 1899 – *Maslakovets, N.A.* (1899). O zanyatiyakh vysochaishe uchrezhdennoi 16-go iyunya 1898 goda Komissii v oblasti voiska Donskogo i o dostignutykh eyu rezul'tatakh: Doklad sostoyashchego v rasporyazhenii voennogo ministra General'nogo shtaba general-leitenanta Maslakovtsa 23 avg. 1899 g. [About the studies of the highest commission established in the field of the Don Army on June 16, 1898 and the results achieved by it: Report of the General Minister of Staff General-Staff Lieutenant-General Maslakovets at his disposal 23 aug. 1899]. SPb., 123 p. [in Russian]

Nash krai, 1963 – *Nash krai: Dokumenty po istorii Donskoi oblasti* [Our land: Documents on the history of the Don region]. Rostov-na-Donu, 1963. 576 p. [in Russian]

Nomikosov, 1884 – *Nomikosov, S.F.* (1884). Statisticheskoe opisanie Oblasti Voiska Donskogo [Statistical description of the Province of the Don army]. Novocherkassk. 774 p. [in Russian]

Petrovskii, 1916 – *Petrovskii, A.I.* (1916). Opis' voiskovym, nakaznym i voiskovym nakaznym atamanam, v raznoe vremya v goroda Cherkassk, a zatem Novocherkassk dlya upravleniya Oblast'yu voiska Donskogo ot vysshego nachal'stva postavlennym. (1738-1916 gg.) [Inventory of troop, felon and troop of atamans, at different times in the city of Cherkassk, and then Novocherkassk to control the Province of the Don army from the highest authorities delivered. (1738-1916)]. Novocherkassk, 40 p. [in Russian]

Protokoly..., 1899 – *Protokoly Komissii po issledovaniyu nuzhd kazach'ego naseleniya Donskoi oblasti* [Protocols of the Commission for the study of the needs of the Cossack population of the Don region]. B.m., 1899. 289 p. [in Russian]

Shevchenko et al., 2016 – *Shevchenko, N.A., Vidishcheva, E.V., Emelyanova, O.V.* (2016). The Establishment of the System of Public Education in the Caucasus (1802–1917 years): the Characteristic Features. *Bylye Gody*, 40(2): 363-372.

Tikidzh'yan, 1998 – *Tikidzh'yan, R.G.* (1908). Voiskovoi nakaznoi ataman, knyaz' N.I. Svyatopolk–Mirskii (1881–1898) [The military ataman, Prince N.I. Svyatopolk – Mirsky (1881–1898)]. *Donskoi vremennik*. [Elektronnyi resurs]. URL: http://donvrem.dspl.ru/Files/article/m3/o/art.aspx?art_id=97 (data obrashcheniya: 17.01.2019). [in Russian]

Volvenko, 2017 – *Volvenko, A.A.* (2017). Ocherki po istorii donsokogo kazachestva v pozdneimperskii period (II pol. XIX – nach. XX vv.) [Essays on the history of the Don Cossacks in the late imperial period (II half XIX – early XX centuries)]. Rostov-na-Donu. 226 p. [in Russian]